

Customer Satisfaction on Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools

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Abstract - Artificial intelligence tools help us to perform various tasks. These tools can understand the language and learn like human. In this research is about to finding how the peoples are satisfied with these AI tools. We want to know that these tools make the people become satisfied or if there are things that could be better. Nowadays we were use AI tools more and more in our daily lives, it's important that to understand how people were feel about them. Through this we can make these tools better and more helpful for everyone. So, let's explore that how AI tools are impact people's happiness and what we can learn to make them even more user-friendly.

Keywords - Artificial Intelligence, customer satisfaction, user experience, creativity perception, problem solving, user feedback, economic impact.

I. INTRODUCTION

AI tools are the smart assistant for computers. They help up to perform various tasks and solve complex problems. They can learn from data, solve problems and make decisions without any explicit programs. It makes the machines more efficient and capable [4]. AI tools are categorized into different fields including machine learning: - it uses algorithm to interpret and analyze the data [12]. Natural Language Processing (NLP): Interprets and Understand human language to facilitate the communication and conversation [2]. Robotics: It an AI integrate to control robots and make their ability to perform different tasks autonomously [6]. In 1950s-1960s where the people came up with the term 'Artificial intelligence' that computers that can think like humans and early researchers focused on making computer understand symbols and solve problems [1]. In 1980s-1990s where the expert system become popular but there were some

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difficulties and this caused a time when people weren't as interested in and did not invest the money in AI [14]. In 1990s-2000s the machine learning became important with algorithms like support vector machines and neural networks [10]. In 2010s deep learning a special kind of machine learning became successful [12]. In 2020s Continued the advancements in AI technologies Nowadays we were use AI tools more and more in our daily lives [8]. It makes the devices smarter and more responsive [4]. Now a days AI tools are significantly changing the world into various ways today like automation and efficiency, healthcare advances, smart assistants and devices, economic impact, education etc. [11]

II. FEATURES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS

- **Automation:** It can automate the task, minimize the requirement for manual intervention and saving time [13].
- **Predictive Analytics:** AI tools can analyze the data and predict what might happen in the future [10].
- **Natural Language Processing (NLP) :** [2] Interprets and Understand human language to facilitate communication and conversation.
- **Problem Solving :** AI tools are good at solving complex problem by processing lot of information and finding the best solution .
- **Personalization :** These tools can personalize the experience by considering what user like and how user usually do things [4].
- **Voice Recognition :** They can listen and understand what users are saying, follow users voice command and communicate with users .

- Computer Vision : Smart tools can see and understand the visual information and display images and videos [12].

a. Some of the Artificial Intelligence Tools

- ChatGPT : It is an chat tool that created by Open AI. It understands and talk with peoples and help them in various questions and tasks [4].
- Decktopus (slides and presentation) : This tools helps you make the presentation more easily. It uses layout, content and algorithm to suggest design, making it simple to create professional looking presentation [3].
- Jasper (Content Creation) : It is an AI tools helps for creating contents, it is easier to generate and show different types of information.[1]
- Descript : It is an AI tool for creating or editing the videos. It automatically edit the videos by listening to the audio and let you control the process with text command.[7]
- Zapier (Automation) tool : It automates the tasks by connecting different apps and allowing them to work together without manual effort. With this tool users can set up “Zaps” to automate tasks and increase efficiency.
- Spline AI (3D Models) : It helps with 3D models. It utilize smart learning to create and enhance 3D design. It is useful for applications like games and animations.[8]

b. Advantages of Artificial intelligence tools

- Automation : AI can automate the task to reduce the need for human to perform repetitive task[11].
- Problem Solving : AI tools helps to find out complex problems faster[6].
- Understand Language : AI devices has the capabilities to facilitate communication by understanding and responding to human speech pattern[5].

c. Disadvantages of Artificial intelligence tools

- Lack of creativity : AI can do certain tasks well, it will struggle to be creative or come up with new ideas like human can.[1]

- Unemployment : Artificial intelligence advancement may replace some jobs .[11]
- Privacy issues : AI devices collecting lots of personal data that can be risky ,raising privacy and security concern.[4]
- Learning Problems : AI machines can may face issues like interruption, errors, or malfunctions which may lead to undesirable or catastrophic consequences.[6]

d. Objectives

- Improve usability and interface design for easier interaction.
- Ensure AI tools effectively address user requirements.
- speed, accuracy, and responsiveness of AI tools.
- Encourage more users to use AI tools by showcasing their value.
- Use feedback to innovate and add new features.
- Continuous Improvement: Regularly update and improve AI tools based on user feedback.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1] Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Customer Experience [1] In this study examines how AI is changing shopping experiences, focusing on beauty products. It uses a theoretical model to analyze the data from an online survey of customers who used AI services from a beauty brand. Findings show that trust, perceived sacrifice, and relationship commitment significantly impact AI enabled user experiences. The research offers insights for retailers using AI in their services.

[2] Customer Satisfaction Towards Artificial Intelligence On Digital Marketing [2] In digital marketing, AI plays a crucial role by enhancing customer satisfaction through intelligent search engines, smarter advertisements, customer segmentation, and predictive customer support.

[3] Role of Artificial intelligence In Tourism and Hospitality Management: [3] Within tourism and hospitality management, the integration of AI technology improves guest services, emphasizing the advantages of robots, automation, and AI in enhancing service quality and management efficiency.

[4] Customer Experiences in the Age of Artificial Intelligence[4] In retail, AI integration enhances shopping experiences by leveraging trust-commitment theory and service quality models, offering practical implications for retailers deploying AI services.

[5] The Influence of AI Chatbots in Fintech Services on Customer Loyalty within the Banking Industry: [5] In the banking sector, AI-powered chatbots influence customer loyalty by optimizing interactions and satisfaction levels, thereby enhancing overall customer experience and loyalty.

[6]. AI redefining the hospitality industry.[6] This paper explore how artificial intelligence technologies have redefined the hospitality industry. It develop a theoretical framework to evaluate its impact on employee engagement retention and productivity levels, stemming from its potential implications for service quality and customer satisfaction.

[7]. The impact of augmented reality on overall service satisfaction in elaborate services capes.[7] The aim of this study is to investigate the guiding help of an AR app in elaborate services capes which typically constitute complex environment.

[8].Artificial intelligence and business intelligence in service of social mobile entrepreneurship.[8] AI and BI can benefit mobile social entrepreneurship. AI helps by automating tasks, analyzing data, and improving user support through chatbots

[9]. A review of AI Tools and customer experience in online fashion retails.[9] This paper aims how Artificial Intelligence (AI) impacts ecommerce and enhances online customer satisfaction. It reviews technological advancements that optimize the user experience, leading to e-satisfaction, and examines its impact on user purchase intention. The goal is to provide businesses and researchers with insights to conduct empirical studies in AI-enabled retails.

[10].Artificial Intelligence in investment management.[10] This paper explores how Artificial Intelligence (AI) revolutionizes investment, asset, and warehouse management. AI analyze financial data for informed investment decisions, monitors asset performance, and optimizes warehouse operations. The impact of AI includes good performance, cost reduction, and improved customer satisfaction.

[11] . Role of Disruptive Technology and Artificial Intelligence in effective logistics and distribution management.[11] This analysis emphasizes how real-time data, aided by artificial intelligence and digital technology, facilitates faster and more accurate decision-making and helps identify market patterns and trends. It mention the significant impact of artificial intelligence on logistics and distribution management, leading to improved supply chain operations and new business opportunities worldwide

[12] . AI Impact on Job Automation. [12] This explore that the AI is transforming many sectors by automating jobs, improving productivity, efficiency, and accuracy. While AI handles repetitive tasks, peoples can focus on creative and strategic work, enhancing job satisfaction. Industries like manufacturing, shipping, and customer service already benefit from AI automation, but there are concerns about job displacement.

[13]. The Impact of Customer Satisfaction on AI chatbots with Anthro morphism as the mediator. [13] This paper explores the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction and their ability to create a human-like presence. AI chatbots, unlike human agents, use pre-installed software to communicate with users, quickly solving queries and providing information.

[14]. Information Tools, AI models and methods used for automatic analysis of customer satisfaction.[14] This paper uses informatics tools and methods to analyze consumer reviews for insights into satisfaction. The results support the use of these methods over traditional qualitative and quantitative research for good decision-making in product quality management.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The survey method employed in this study involved collecting data from participants regarding their usage, satisfaction, and perceptions of AI tools. Data collection was conducted using an online platform called google form.166 responses were collected through google form and the data will helps to understand how AI tools impact customer satisfaction. The data were analyzed using statistical techniques such as chi-squared tests and ANOVA to test hypothesis related to users' likelihood of recommendation, satisfaction levels, perceived ease of use, creativity, and continued usage of AI tools. The findings provide insights into the factors influencing customer satisfaction and highlight areas for improvement in the design and

implementation of AI technologies to enhance user experiences. Overall, the study contributes to our understanding of how AI tools impact customer happiness and satisfaction in different contexts.

a. Data Interpretation

Figure 1 : Relationship between the likelihood of recommending AI tools and whether the individuals have utilized such tools

In Figure 1 this crosstabulation compares how likely people are to recommend AI tools based on whether they've used them. It seems that the people who have used AI tools are more likely to recommend them. For instance, among those very likely to recommend, most have used the tools. On the other hand, those who haven't used AI tools are less likely to recommend them. The chi-square test is likely used here to determine if there's a significant association between the likelihood of recommendation and use of AI tools, suggesting that there might indeed be a relationship between the two factors.

Figure 2 : relationship between user's perceptions of a tools ease of use and their reported encounters with issues while using it

In Figure 2 this crosstabulation looks at how easy people found a tool to use and whether they encountered issues with it. It shows that individuals who rated the tool as "easy to use" experienced fewer issues compared to those who rated it as "neutral." Conversely, individuals who rated the tool as "neutral" encountered issues more frequently. The "not sure" category in encountered issues has a moderate count across both user-friendly rating groups. This comparison likely used a chi-square test to assess if there's a significant association between user-friendly ratings and encountered issues, suggesting that there might indeed be a relationship between the two factors.

Figure 3 : analysing the relationship between individuals' likelihood of continuing to use a tools and their perception of its creativity.

In Figure 3 this crosstabulation examines how likely people are to continue using a tool based on their perception of its creativity. It shows that individuals who are very likely to continue using the tool tend to perceive it as more creative, whereas those who are neutral or unlikely to continue usage tend to view it as equally or less creative. Among those likely to continue usage, there's a higher proportion perceiving the tool as more creative. The comparison likely used a chi-square test to determine if there's a significant association between likelihood of continued usage and creativity comparison, suggesting a potential relationship between these factors.

Figure 4 : Relationship between users' likelihood of continuing to use a tools and their overall performance rating of the tool

In Figure 4 this crosstabulation examines the likelihood of continued usage of a tool in relation to the overall performance rating given by users. It reveals that individuals who are very likely to continue using the tool tend to rate its overall performance as either excellent or good. Conversely, those who are unlikely to continue usage tend to rate the tool's performance lower, often as average. Among those likely to continue usage, there's a mix of ratings, but a higher proportion rates the performance as good. The comparison likely used a chi-square test to assess if there's a significant association between likelihood of continued usage and overall performance rating, indicating a potential relationship between these factors.

Figure 5 : comparing different perceptions of creativity and their impact on satisfaction_with tools.

In Figure 5 the comparison conducted in this analysis is the between different perceptions of creativity ("More Creative," "Equally Creative," and "Less Creative") regarding their impact on satisfaction with tools. The statistical test used is a one-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) to

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determine if there are significant differences in satisfaction scores among the creativity comparison groups.

Figure 6 : Compare satisfaction with the tools across different levels of ease of learning.

Figure 6 In this analysis a one-way ANOVA was conducted to compare satisfaction with tools across different levels of ease of learning. The variable used for comparison is "satisfaction_with_tools," representing customers satisfaction ratings, while the independent variable is "ease_of_learning," representing users' perceptions of how easy it was to learn the tools. The ANOVA test results indicate a significant difference in satisfaction scores among the ease of learning groups ($F(4, 161) = 4.706, p = .001$), with an effect size (Eta-squared) of .105. This suggests that the perceived ease of learning the tools influences users' satisfaction with them.

Figure 7 : Compare satisfaction with the tools across different parts of the AI tool perceived as most useful

Figure 7 In this analysis a one-way ANOVA was conducted to compare satisfaction with tools across different parts of the AI tool perceived as

most useful. The variable used for comparison is "satisfaction_with_tools," representing users' satisfaction ratings, while the independent variable is "most_useful_ai_tool_part," representing customers' perceptions of the most useful part of the AI tool.

V. CONCLUSION

In this research paper we have explored how people feel about AI tools. We have seen that these tools were helpful in many ways, also raise concerns like job loss and privacy issues. Our study found that customers are more likely to recommend AI tools if they find them easy to use and creative. By understanding the user feedback and improving these tools we can make them even more useful and user-friendly. Overall, this research highlights the importance of considering people's experiences to make AI tools better for everyone and how people are satisfied with these AI tools.

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